

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF BUPRENORPHINE
BUCCAL TABLETS****CH.Kantlam¹, G. Renuka^{2*}, Shivaleela Suguru³, Syeda Sadaf Makki³, Thalari Sahish³,
Varre Shirisha Reddy³, Yanabothula Komalika³.**¹ Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, Brilliant College of Pharmacy, Abdullapurmet Village, Hayathnagar, Rangareddy, Telangana.² Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, Brilliant College of Pharmacy, Abdullapurmet Village, Hayathnagar, Rangareddy, Telangana.³ Department of Pharmaceutics, Brilliant College of Pharmacy, Abdullapurmet Village, Hayathnagar, Rangareddy, Telangana.**Abstract:**

Buccal tablet of oral formulations of these drugs have been developed to improve their acceptability to patients and thus improve compliance. The focus of present investigation was to improve solubility, bioavailability and to achieved rapid onset action. Buccal tablets of Buprenorphine were prepared by direct compression technique. Four Formulations were formulated using Ethyl cellulose and Carboxy methyl cellulose sodium as polymers on Swelling index, Disintegration time. In addition, the prepared tablets were also evaluated for weight variation, thickness, moisture absorption, friability, content uniformity, wetting time and drug release studies. Formulation reveals fast dissolution and disintegration rate of optimized Buprenorphine buccal tablets.

Key words: Buprenorphine, Direct compression technique, FTIR studies, Synthetic polymer, Drug release studies.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Ch. Kantlam,**

Department of Pharmaceutics,
Brilliant College of Pharmacy,
Abdullapurmet Village,
Hayath Nagar,
Rangareddy, Telangana

QR CODE

Please cite this article in press **Ch. Kantlam et al., Formulation And Evaluation Of Buprenorphine Buccal Tablets., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12(07).**

1. INTRODUCTION:

Administration of a drug via the buccal mucosa (the lining of the cheek) to the systemic circulation is defined as buccal delivery. Despite, the buccal mucosa is significantly less permeable than the sublingual mucosa and usually not able to provide rapid drug absorption or good bioavailability, it is relatively more permeable than the skin and also offers other advantage over alternative delivery routes¹. The fact that the buccal mucosa is less permeable than sublingual floor makes it more desirable site for sustained drug delivery. Apart from avoiding enzymatic degradation and first pass metabolism, the non-acidic conditions and lipophilic nature of the buccal tissue provide potential and promises for successful delivery of peptide and proteins². Tablets have been the most commonly investigated dosage form for buccal drug delivery to date. Buccal tablets are small, flat and oval with a diameter of approximately 5–8 mm. Unlike conventional tablets, buccal mucoadhesive tablets allow for drinking and speaking without major discomfort³. They soften, adhere to the mucosa, and are retained in position until dissolution and/or release is complete. These tablets can be applied to different sites in the oral cavity, including the palate, the mucosa lining the cheek as well as between the lip and the gum. Successive tablets can be applied to alternate sides of the mouth. The major drawback of buccal bioadhesive tablets is their lack of physical flexibility, leading to poor patient compliance for long-term and repeated dose⁴. Bioadhesive tablets are usually prepared by direct compression, but wet

granulation techniques can also be used.⁵ Tablets intended for buccal administration by insertion into the buccal pouch may dissolve or erode slowly; therefore, they are formulated and compressed with sufficient pressure only to give a hard tablet⁶. The focus of present investigation was to improve solubility, bioavailability and to achieved rapid onset action. Buccal tablets of Buprenorphine were prepared by direct compression technique the prepared tablets were also evaluated for weight variation, thickness, moisture absorption, friability, content uniformity, wetting time and drug release studies.

Drug excipient compatibility studies⁷

Drug excipients compatibility studies were performed to know the compatibility of excipient with drug at accelerated conditions. The study was conducted by preparing homogenous mixture of excipients with drug and filled in HDPE bags and LDPE bags. Glass vials were exposed to 600 C and 400C/75 %RH for 4 weeks and LDPE bags were exposed to 400C±75 %RH for 4 weeks. Samples were observed periodically for any physical change.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Buprenorphine was collected as a gift sample from Hetero labs, Hyderabad and various excipients and polymers were purchased from AR chemicals, Hyderabad.

2.1 METHODOLOGY

Formulation Development

Table-1: Formulation table

S.NO.	INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3	F4
1	Buprenorphine	8	8	8	8
2	Ethyl cellulose	25	50	-	-
3	Carboxy methyl cellulose Sodium	-	-	25	50
4	Lactose	50	25	50	25
5	Aspartame	2	2	2	2
6	Microcrystalline Cellulose	10	10	10	10
7	Magnesium stearate	3	3	3	3
8	Talc	2	2	2	2
9	Total Wt	100	100	100	100

Preparation method

Buccal tablet formulations of Buprenorphine were prepared by direct compression method. Two different grades of Carboxy methyl cellulose sodium and ethyl cellulose were used as release retardant materials. Magnesium stearate and talc were used as lubricant/glidants. Sufficient quantities of microcrystalline cellulose were used to raise the total bulk of the tablets to a weight of 100 mg each. All the ingredients were passed through sieve # 44 before mixing. Initially drug and polymers were mixed thoroughly and then required quantities of fillers were added and finally the blend was mixed with talc thoroughly for 5min in a poly bag and then required amount of magnesium stearate was added

and mixed for another 5min. Powder blends (for 20 tablets each) of all the above formulations were compressed on single punch tablet press using 8mm punches⁸.

(round shape) to the hardness of 5 Kg/cm².

Evaluation parameters^{9,10,11}

Pre compression parameters

Bulk density:

Accurately weighed quantities of the pellets added to the cylinder with the aid of a funnel. Typically, the initial volume was noted and the sample was then tapped until no further reduction in volume was noted. The volumes before and after tapping were

used on the standard equation to compute bulk and tapped density respectively.

$LBD = Wt \text{ of powder} / \text{Volume of powder.}$

$TBD = Wt \text{ of powder} / \text{Tapped volume of powder}$

Compressibility index:

The compressibility index and the closely related Hausner's ratio have become the simple fast and popular methods of predicting powder flow characteristics. The compressibility index has been proposed as an indirect measure of bulk density, size and shape, surface area, moisture content and cohesiveness of materials. Both are determined by measuring both the bulk volume and tapped volume of a powder. The basic procedure is to measure the unsettled apparent volume and the final tapped volume of the powder after tapping the material until no further volume changes occur. The compressibility index and the Hausner's ratio calculated as follows:

$\text{Carr's index (\%)} = [(TBD - LBD) \times 100] / TBD$

Hausner ratio

$\text{Hausner ratio} = TBD / LBD$

Angle of repose:

The angle of repose determined by funnel method. The accurately weighed powder blend taken in a funnel. The height of the funnel adjusted in such a way that the tip of the funnel just touched the apex of the heap of the powder blend. The blends allowed to flow freely onto the surface. The diameter of the powder cone measured and angle of repose calculated using the following equation:
 $\tan \theta = h/r$

Drug content

Ten tablets were weighed and powdered in a mortar. Accurately weighed tablet powder samples equivalent to 20mg of Buprenorphine was transferred to a 100mL volumetric flask, and the Buprenorphine was extracted into 75mL methanol and then finally the volume was made to 100 mL with methanol. This solution was suitably diluted with 6.8 phosphate buffer and the absorbance was measured at 268 nm. The estimations were carried out in triplicate. Uniformity of weight of tablets. The individual and total weight of 20 tablets from each batch was determined. Percentage deviation of the individual weights from the average weights was calculated.

Hardness

The hardness of the tablets was measured with a Pfizer hardness tester. The results reported were average of 6 tablets for each formulation.

Friability

For each formulation 10 tablets were weighed, placed in Friabilator and were subjected to 100 rotations in 4min. The tablets were reweighed and friability was calculated by the following formula:

$\text{Friability} = (W_2 - W_1) / W_1$

Disintegration Time:

In the presented studies, three different types of in vitro methods of tablet disintegration were used: those where the only factor leading to the disintegration was water wicking into the matrix of the tablet, the tests with water agitation or stirring, and the methods where direct destructive forces were put on the tested tablet, such as grinding or pressing with additional weight. Therefore, disintegration tests showed great variability in the data measured with different methods.

Swelling index studies

The swelling study was performed on petri dishes containing 1% agar gel. Four tablets were weighed and placed in a petri dish. The petri dishes contained 4 tablets, and each was placed in an incubator at $37^\circ\text{C} \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. After 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3 hours, excess water on the surface was carefully removed using the filter paper without pressing. The tablets were reweighed and the swelling index was calculated using the formula:

$\text{Swelling Index} = \frac{W_i - W_f}{W_i} \times 100$

Appropriate swelling property of buccal formulations is needed for proper adhesion

Dissolution studies

In vitro dissolution studies of Buprenorphine buccal tablets formulations prepared were carried out in 900mL of 6.8 phosphate buffer using USP type II (paddle method) Dissolution Rate Test Apparatus (DISSO 8000, Lab India). The tablet was placed in a sinker and placed in to the dissolution medium. A speed of 100 rpm and a temperature of $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ were used in each test. A 5mL aliquot was withdrawn at different time intervals, and replaced with 5mL of fresh dissolution medium. The filtered samples were suitably diluted if necessary and assayed for Buprenorphine by measuring absorbance at 268nm. The dissolution experiments were carried out in triplicate.

Stability studies

Stability studies were carried out of the most satisfactory formulation F4, at $30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C} / 65 \pm 5\% \text{RH}$ and $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C} / 75 \pm 5\% \text{RH}$ for two months to assess their long term stability as per ICH guidelines. At various time intervals of 30 days and 60 days and 90 days samples were evaluated. There was no major change in the various physicochemical

parameters evaluated like hardness, drug content, in vitro dissolution pattern at the various sampling points. There was no statistically significant difference between the initial values and the results obtained during stability studies.

3.RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

FT-IR Spectrum of Buprenorphine

FT-IR Spectra of Buprenorphine and excipients were recorded. All these peaks have appeared in formulation and physical mixture, indicating no chemical interaction between Buprenorphine and superdisintegrant. It also confirmed that the stability of drug during microencapsulation process.

SHIMADZU

Fig-1: FTIR Spectra of Buprenorphine

SHIMADZU

Fig-2: FTIR Spectra of physical mixture of drug and excipients

Compatibility studies were performed using IR spectrophotometer. The IR spectrum of pure drug

and physical mixture of drug and excipients were studied. The characteristic absorption of peaks

were obtained as above and as they were in official limits ($\pm 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) the drug is compatible with excipients.

Evaluation studies

Pre compression parameters

- a) **Bulk Density:** The bulk density for the formulated blend was carried out for all formulation and found in the range of 0.428-0.439.
- b) **Tapped density:** The tapped density for the formulated blend was carried out for all

formulation and found in the range of 0.538-0.552.

c) **Angle of repose:** The angle of repose for the formulated blend was carried out. It concludes that all the formulations blend was found to be in the range of 27 to 30°

d) **Compressibility index:** Compressibility index was carried out, it found between 16.25% to 17.98 % indicating the powder blend have the required flow property for compression.

Characterization of Formulation

Table-2: Pre compression parameters of Buprenorphine buccal tablets

S. no	Bulk density	Tapped density	Compressibility index	Hausner ratio	ANGLE OF REPOSE
F1	0.438	0.547	17.98	1.19	29°c
F2	0.435	0.552	16.89	1.20	30°c
F3	0.439	0.550	16.25	1.26	27°c
F4	0.428	0.538	17.85	1.24	30°c

Post compression parameters

Weight variation:

All the formulated (F1 to F4) tablets passed weight variation test as the % weight variation was within the pharmacopoeial limits of $\pm 7.5\%$ of the weight. The weights of all the tablets were found to be uniform with low standard deviation values.

Thickness:

Tablets mean thickness were uniform in F1 to F4 formulations and were found to be in the range of 3.1 mm to 3.8 mm.

Hardness:

The measured hardness of tablets of each batch ranged between 3.36 to 3.58 kg/cm^2 . This ensures good handling characteristics of all batches.

Friability:

The % friability was less than 1% in all the formulations ensuring that the tablets were mechanically stable.

Content Uniformity:

The percentage of drug content for F1 to F4 was found to be between 79.83 % to 85.63% of Buprenorphine, it complies with official specifications.

Disintegration Time:

The Disintegration time for F1 to F4 was found to be between 12 to 16 % of Buprenorphine, it complies with official specifications

Swelling index:

The swelling index for F1 to F4 was found to be between 100 to 113 % of Buprenorphine , it complies with official specifications.

Table-3: Evaluation parameters of Buprenorphine tablets

F. No.	Weight variation (mg)	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (kg/cm^2)	Friability (%)	Drug Content (%)	Disintegration time (min)	Swelling index
F1	99	3.6	3.36	0.52	83.69	15	110
F2	100	3.1	3.40	0.46	79.83	16	113
F3	101	3.8	3.52	0.53	84.12	14	102
F4	100	3.4	3.58	0.50	85.63	12	100

Dissolution studies

All the 4 formulation of Buprenorphine buccal tablets were subjected to in vitro drug release studies these studies were carried out using dissolution apparatus. The dissolution medium consisted of 900 ml of Standard buffer pH 6.8 for period of time.

Table-4: Drug release studies of all formulations

Time	F1	F2	F3	F4
0	0	0	0	0
1	18.63	19.68	20.13	21.25
2	25.19	26.37	31.20	32.50
3	35.60	37.89	40.12	42.37
4	48.79	49.82	51.28	55.68
5	58.63	57.66	65.52	67.80
6	66.78	68.80	72.13	73.55
7	75.89	76.93	81.26	85.10
8	90.12	94.63	95.68	97.82

Table-3: Dissolution Profile of F1to F4 formulations**Stability Study**

There was no significant change in physical and chemical properties of the buccal tablets of formulation F-4 after 90 days. Parameters quantified at various time intervals were shown.

Table-5: Stability studies of all formulations

Formulation Code	Parameters	Initial	1 st Month	2 nd Month	3 rd Month	Limits as per Specifications
F-4	25 ^o C/60%RH % Release	97.82	96.83	95.75	94.37	Not less than 85 %
F-4	30 ^o C/75% RH % Release	97.82	96.25	95.52	94.63	Not less than 85 %
F-4	40 ^o C/75% RH % Release	97.82	96.10	95.50	94.22	Not less than 85 %

3.CONCLUSION:

The present study was undertaken with an aim to formulate and evaluate Buprenorphine buccal tablets using different polymers as release retarding agents. Preformulation study was carried out and all the parameters were found within the specification.

Hence different batches of Buprenorphine were prepared using selected excipients. Powders were evaluated for Bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index, Hausner ratio before being punched as tablets.

Various formulations of sustained release tablets of Buprenorphine were prepared by using different polymers in different proportions by direct compression technique. The tablets were evaluated for physical parameters, *in vitro* release study and stability studies. In-vitro release indicated that the formulation F4 had better dissolution profile along with sustained action as compare to other formulations. Tablets were evaluated for hardness, friability, in-vitro release profile and drug content. No significant changes were observed in any of the studied parameters during the study period (90days), thus it could be concluded that formulation was stable. From the results it can be concluded that buccal drug release tablet of Buprenorphine containing ethyl cellulose i.e. F4 can be formulated successfully.

4.REFERENCES:

1. Shoba Rani R Hiremath; Industrial Pharmacy, Orient Longman private limited, 2008; First edition, 73-77.
2. Sang-Chul Shin, Jin-Pil Bum, Jun-Shik Choi. Enhanced bioavailability by buccal administration of triamcinolone acetonide from the bioadhesive gels in rabbits, Int. J. Pharmaceutics., 2009; 209:37-43.
3. Giradkar KP, Design development and in vitro evaluation of bioadhesive dosage form for buccal route, International journal of pharma research & development, 2010, 2.
4. Giradkar MA, Channawar AD, Kajale E, Sridhar RS, Kamble BV, Chandewar. Design, development and in vitro evaluation of bioadhesive dosage form for buccal route. Int. J. Pharm. Res. Dev., 2010; 2(6):1-20.
5. Calum R, Park, Dale L, Munday. Development and evaluation of a biphasic buccal adhesive tablet for nicotine replacement therapy. Int. J. Pharm., 2002; 237:215-26.
6. Subhash V, Madhuri Channawar, Anil V, Unmesh, Kailash R. Chitosan based sustained release mucoadhesive buccal patches Containing verapamil HCl, Int. J. Pharm. Pharm. Sci., 2009; 1(1): 216-29.
7. Bhongiri B, Ramachandran V, Kumar RS. Preformulation Studies Of S-Equol. Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results. 2022 Oct 5;13.
8. Edsman K, Pharmaceutical applications of mucoadhesion for the non-oral routes, Journal of pharmacy & pharmacology, 2005, 57, 3-19.
9. Surender Verma, MahimaKaul, ArunaRawat, SapnaSaini. An overview on buccal drug delivery system. Int J Pharm Sci Res 2011;2(6):1303-21.
10. Miller NS, Johnston TP. The use of mucoadhesive polymers in buccal drug delivery, Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews 2005;57:1666-91.
11. Patel KV, Patel ND, Dodiya HD, Shelat PK. Buccal bioadhesive drug delivery system: An Overview. Int J Pharm Bio Arch 2011;2(2): 600-9.